

Central Carbon-bonded Thenoyltrifluoroacetato Complexes of Palladium(II)

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Acetylacetone is a versatile ligand, usually the anion coordinates¹ to a metal ion through the oxygen atoms completing a six-membered chelate ring. The unidentate linkage through the γ -carbon atom is also known for Pt^{II}^{2,3} and Pd^{II}³. Also a terminal carbon bonded complex of the composition [Pd(acac)Cl.(bpy)] has been reported⁴. In continuation of our investigations⁵ on various linkage modes of a number of β -diketones to Pd^{II} and Pt^{II}, we have studied the reaction of bis(thenoyltrifluoroacetato)palladium(II) with Lewis bases to evaluate the preferential bonding site. The isolation of the γ -carbon bonded thenoyltrifluoroacetato complexes of palladium(II) of the composition [Pd(tta)(C³-tta)(B)] is reported in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

The compounds have the composition [Pd(tta)₂B], where B is the phosphorus or nitrogen base and tta the chelated thenoyl trifluoroacetate anion. These are soluble in acetone, methanol, chloroform, dichloromethane and benzene. Molecular weight data of the triphenyl phosphine compound in chloroform by cryoscopic method indicate it to be monomeric.

Characteristic ir bands of the carbon-bonded complexes are listed in Table 1. Pd(tta)₂ has bands at 1 564, 1 535, 1 505 cm⁻¹ attributed to $\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=C}$ modes. The carbon-bonded complexes show one sharp band around 1 710–1 714 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{C=O}$ of the γ -carbon bonded tta group. The other set of bands found around 1 570, 1 530, 1 508 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the $\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=C}$ modes of the chelated tta molecule. There are many absorption bands due to the coordinated bases, but the most characteristic band of the phosphine was observed at 1 630 cm⁻¹

and of nitrogen bases at 1 620 cm⁻¹. In the far-infrared spectra, the strong band found around 545 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{Pd-C} and the other strong band at ~460 cm⁻¹ to ν_{Pd-O} , and ν_{Pd-N} band has been observed at ~355 cm⁻¹ in the complexes with nitrogen bases.

The existence of one oxygen-bonded and one carbon-bonded thenoyl trifluoroacetate ligand in the complexes is confirmed by the proton-nmr spectra (Table 1). In Pd(tta)₂, the CH proton signal was observed at δ 6.44 and the thenoyl protons at δ 7–8. In case of the γ -carbon-bonded complexes, there are two distinct set of CH proton signals — δ 6.22–6.33 is attributed to that of chelating tta molecule and that at δ 5.2–5.44 is assigned to the methine signal of the central carbon-bonded tta molecule. Thenoyl group proton signal observed at δ 7–8 also contains the signals due to substituted pyridines and other bases. Assignments have been made in comparison with the spectra of γ -carbon-bonded acetylacetono complexes of palladium(II) and platinum(II). These observations confirm the formation of C³-carbon-bonded tta (thenoyl trifluoroacetate) complexes of palladium(II) as shown by the following structure.

TABLE 1—IR (cm⁻¹) AND ¹H Nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd.**	$\nu_{C=O}$ C-bonded tta	$\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=C}$ O-bonded tta	ν_{max} Phosphine or pyridine bond	δ	
				CH O-bonded tta	CH C ³ -Carbon- bonded tta
Pd(tta)(C ³ -tta)(PPh ₃)	1 712	1 572, 1 540, 1 505	1 632	6.26	5.4 $J_{p-H} = 6.3$ Hz
Pd(tta)(C ³ -tta)(t-pTP)	1 710	1 565, 1 530, 1 510	1 630	6.22	5.2
Pd(tta)(C ³ -tta)(α -pic)	1 710	1 570, 1 531, 1 560	1 620	6.38	5.36
Pd(tta)(C ³ -tta)(2,6-lut)	1 714	1 572, 1 531, 1 508	1 620	6.32	5.44

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**tta = Chelated thenoyltrifluoroacetone, C³-tta = γ -carbon-bonded tta, t-pTp = tris-*p*-toluylphosphine, α -pic = 2-methylpyridine, 2,6-lut = 2,6-dimethylpyridine.

It is pertinent to mention here that γ -carbon-bonded complexes of acetylacetonone could not be obtained with a sterically hindered base like 2,6-lutidine and even though γ -carbon-bonded complexes were obtained with 3- or 4-picoline as bases in the present case, instead complexes of the type $[\text{PdB}_4](\text{tta})_2$ were obtained which contain the tta anion in the outer sphere ($\beta = 3$ - or 4-picoline).

Experimental

$\text{Pd}(\text{tta})_2$ was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 cm^3). An equimolar amount of triphenylphosphine was dissolved in dichloromethane (5 cm^3). The solutions were mixed and stirred at room temperature for 5 h. The solution was concentrated to 5 cm^3 by a rotary vacuum evaporator and treated with petroleum ether (10 cm^3) and kept in a refrigerator overnight. The sticky mass was digested with small amount of dichloromethane and petroleum ether (1 : 1) to produce a yellow powder which was crystallised from dichloromethane-petroleum ether mixture. Compound using tris-*p*-toluyl phosphine as a base was prepared in a similar manner.

$\text{Pd}(\text{tta})_2$ (0.3 g) was suspended in α -picoline (3 cm^3) and stirred at 40° for 0.5 h. The resulting clear solution was treated with petroleum ether (4 cm^3) and kept in a refrigerator overnight to produce a sticky yellow oil. On digestion with small amount of dichloromethane and petroleum ether several times and keeping in a refrigerator

for several days, it produced a yellow powder which was crystallised from dichloromethane-petroleum ether. Compound with 2,6-lutidine was prepared using similar procedure. Compounds were characterised by C, H, N analyses. Molecular weight of the triphenyl phosphine compound was found to be 775 (calcd. 811).

Ir spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer 337 and Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometers and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a JEOL-JNM spectrometer (100 MHz) using tetramethylsilane as internal reference.

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